

Research Article

Comparative Seismic Assessment and Strengthening of Two Storey URM Dwellings in Kruja Insights from Four Case Studies

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Abstract

This paper examines four two-storey unreinforced masonry (URM) houses in Kruja, Albania, all of which were heavily damaged during the 26 November 2019 earthquake. Although the buildings were constructed at different times and by different owners, they share similar materials, wall configurations and construction practices. Because of this, they also show comparable weak points when exposed to strong seismic shaking. The study combines field observations, crack pattern documentation, and nonlinear static (pushover) analysis to understand how these dwellings behaved during the earthquake and why their performance was inadequate. Across all four houses, the most common issues include poor-quality mortar, a lack of proper connections between walls and floor slabs, discontinuous diaphragms, and the absence of any confinement elements. These weaknesses contributed to diagonal cracking, corner separation, partial out-of-plane failures, and significant permanent deformation. Based on the similarities identified in the case studies, a single strengthening concept was developed for the group. The proposed retrofit, which relies mainly on perimeter reinforced-concrete columns, diaphragm improvements, and local wall rehabilitation, aims to address the recurring problems found in this type of construction. The results indicate that this unified approach can substantially increase lateral strength and deformation capacity, particularly in the transverse direction where the original buildings performed poorly. By treating these four dwellings as part of the same typology, the study shows that a consistent and replicable retrofit strategy can be applied to a wider stock of URM houses with similar characteristics in the Kruja region.

Keywords: Unreinforced Masonry, Seismic Assessment, Damage Patterns, Strengthening, Retrofit Strategy.

1. Introduction

Unreinforced masonry (URM) houses are among the most common types of residential construction in Albania, especially in towns like Kruja where many dwellings were built several decades ago without any formal seismic design [1]. These buildings usually rely entirely on load-bearing brick masonry walls, often made with low-strength mortar and without any form of confinement or ductile detailing [2-6]. Over time, natural

deterioration, past interventions, and variations in construction practice have further reduced their capacity to resist lateral loads.

The earthquake of 26 November 2019, with moment magnitude $M_w 6.4$, exposed the weaknesses of this building stock. Many URM houses in Kruja experienced severe structural damage, classified as Damage State 4 (DS-4), with widespread cracking, wall separation, partial out-of-plane failures, and damage concentrated around openings [1, 7]. In most cases, the failure mechanisms reflected well-known deficiencies of older masonry construction: poor wall connections, weak diaphragms, irregular layouts, and the absence of a continuous box-like behaviour.

This paper examines four such URM dwellings from Kruja, all of which suffered heavy damage during the earthquake. Although the houses were not constructed at the same time and differ slightly in layout, they share a similar typology and display comparable structural problems. By analysing them together, the goal is to gain a clearer understanding of the recurring vulnerabilities that affect this category of buildings. The study combines on-site observations, damage surveys, and nonlinear static analyses to provide a complete picture of their seismic response [8-12].

In addition to evaluating their existing condition, a unified strengthening approach is proposed. The idea is that since these buildings share the same weaknesses, they can also benefit from the same type of retrofit solution. The concept focuses on perimeter reinforced-concrete columns, diaphragm improvement, and local enhancements to the masonry walls. This approach aims to make strengthening interventions more consistent, scalable and easier to apply to a broader stock of similar houses throughout the region.

2. Description of Case Study Building

This study examines four representative two-storey unreinforced masonry (URM) dwellings located in Kruja, Albania. All buildings suffered severe structural damage (DS-4) during the 26 November 2019 earthquake. Despite being built independently and at different times, the four dwellings share similar construction characteristics, materials, and failure mechanisms, making them ideal for a comparative typology-based assessment.

2.1 External Reinforcement or Jacketing

Before describing each house separately, it is useful to highlight a set of recurring features that all four buildings have in common [13-17]:

- Two-storey residential layout with similar footprints
- External and internal load-bearing walls constructed from brick or mixed masonry, generally 25–38 cm thick
- Low-strength mortar, typically in the range of 2–3 MPa
- Lack of ring beams or boundary elements at floor levels
- Diaphragms that are either weak, partially damaged, or not adequately connected to the walls

- Traditional wooden roof systems
- Shallow foundation strips without proper reinforcement
- No seismic detailing, no confinement, and limited wall-to-wall interlocking

Due to all four buildings share this typology, many of the damage patterns observed later in the paper follow similar trends.

2.2 Building A

Building A is a two-storey dwelling constructed with solid brick masonry walls. Exterior walls range between 30 and 38 cm in thickness, with interior partitions made of lighter masonry or blockwork, see Figure 1. The structural layout is relatively simple, but the walls are poorly connected at corners, which contributed to the heavy seismic damage observed.

Typical issues identified during inspection include extensive diagonal cracking, wall separation at edges, and signs of out-of-plane movement in the façade. This building is representative of many older URM houses in Kruja.

Figure 1. Building A

2.3 Building B

Building B follows the same general construction tradition but includes wider openings on the ground floor, which reduce the effective shear area of the walls. The use of relatively weak masonry units and deteriorated mortar further contributed to its poor performance, see Figure 2.

The most severe damage occurred on the lower floor, where long X-shaped cracks formed on the primary shear walls. Additional localized damage occurred near door and window openings, where crushing and diagonal cracking were clearly visible.

Figure 2. Building B

2.4 Building C

Building C is characterized by long unconfined masonry walls with limited transverse support, making it vulnerable to both in-plane and out-of-plane actions, see Figure 3. The mortar was found to be highly degraded, which accelerated the formation of sliding cracks during the earthquake.

Several wall panels showed advanced diagonal cracking, and portions of the upper storey exhibited out-of-plane displacement. The building experienced one of the most severe corner separations among the four case studies.

Figure 3. Building C

2.6 Building D

Building D, although similar in size and materials to the other houses, contains more irregular wall layouts and non-uniform wall thicknesses across the façade. This

irregularity led to uneven distribution of lateral forces and more localized failures, see Figure 4.

Observed damage included strong shear cracking, wall splitting at corners, partial detachment of interior partitions, and noticeable roof displacement. The combination of weak materials and irregular geometry explains its DS-4 damage level.

Figure 4. Building D

3. Observed Damage and Failure Mechanisms

The four URM dwellings examined in this study showed a very similar pattern of structural damage after the 2019 earthquake. Even though the houses differ slightly in layout and construction details, the main failure mechanisms were almost identical, reflecting the weaknesses that are typical for this type of masonry construction. The descriptions below summarise the most common forms of damage found during the field inspections.

3.1 Diagonal Shear Cracks in Load-Bearing Walls

One of the most widespread and visible forms of damage in all four buildings was diagonal shear cracking. These cracks usually appeared as long X-shaped patterns running across the main load-bearing walls, particularly on the ground floor where lateral forces are concentrated. The cracks often extended from corner to corner of the wall and passed through mortar joints, indicating low shear strength and brittle behaviour. Walls with large openings or reduced cross-section tended to crack more severely, and in a few cases the masonry near the base of the wall also showed signs of sliding or crushing.

3.2 Separation at Corners and Wall Junctions

Another common issue was the formation of vertical cracks at the corners of the buildings, where orthogonal walls should ideally be well interlocked. In these houses, however, the interlocking was weak or missing, which caused the corners to open during shaking. In some dwellings the cracks reached several centimetres in width, and parts of the wall

edges had slightly rotated or shifted outward, see Figure 5. This type of damage compromises the overall “box behaviour” of the structure and makes the building much more vulnerable to additional shaking.

Figure 5. Damage patterns on building B

3.3 Out-of-Plane Wall Movements

Because the floors in these buildings do not act as strong diaphragms, many of the masonry walls were left unsupported against out-of-plane forces. As a result, signs of bulging, rotation, or partial detachment were visible in several façade walls, especially near the upper storey. In a few cases, small sections of wall at roof level had partially collapsed outward. This mechanism is particularly dangerous because it can occur suddenly and does not require very large deformations.

3.4 Out-of-Plane Wall Movements

All four dwellings showed cracking or detachment along the connection between the walls and the floor slabs. This occurred in both directions, but it was especially noticeable where timber or weak slab systems were present. The cracks typically followed the horizontal interface line, indicating that the diaphragms were not transferring lateral forces effectively. In some houses, parts of the slab appeared to have separated or shifted slightly relative to the supporting walls, see Figure 6.

Figure 6. Damage patterns on building D

3.5 Damage Concentrated Around Openings

Openings such as doors and windows acted as weak points in the structural system. Most buildings exhibited diagonal cracks starting from the corners of openings or crushing directly above lintels. Wide openings, especially in Building B, contributed to more severe damage because they reduced the effective shear resistance of the walls. In some cases, infill sections around openings partially detached from the surrounding masonry, see Figure 7.

Figure 7. Damage patterns on building A

3.6 Material Degradation and Mortar Weakness

A final but important factor observed across all four dwellings was the general deterioration of the masonry materials. The mortar was often powdery and friable, and in many locations it had completely lost adhesion. This condition made the walls much more prone to cracking and sliding. In buildings where moisture had been a problem, the masonry units themselves were also weakened. These issues directly contributed to the poor seismic performance and to the DS-4 classification in all buildings.

3.7 Summary of Failure Patterns

Taken together, the field observations show that the four URM buildings responded in a very similar way to earthquake shaking. Their behaviour was dominated by brittle shear failure, loss of box action, diaphragm weaknesses, and out-of-plane instability all typical of older masonry houses built without seismic considerations. These findings align well with the results of the nonlinear analyses presented in the next chapter.

4. Structural Assessment

The structural behavior of the four URM dwellings was evaluated through nonlinear static (pushover) analysis, using the models developed during the technical assessment phase. Although each building has its own geometric layout and internal configuration, the analytical results reveal a very similar seismic response across the group [18-23]. This is

expected, given their matching construction typology, weak materials, and limited lateral-load resistance. The assessment focused on understanding how each structure behaves once cracking begins, how quickly stiffness deteriorates, and whether the displacement capacity is sufficient to meet the performance levels required by Eurocode 8. The results confirmed the weaknesses already observed during the field inspections, providing a clearer picture of the mechanisms that govern their response.

4.1 Modelling Approach and Key Assumptions

All buildings were analysed using the equivalent-frame methodology that is commonly applied to masonry structures. Masonry walls were represented through nonlinear macro-elements piers and spandrels capable of capturing both shear and flexural failure. Although the buildings differ in plan layout, the modelling assumptions were kept as consistent as possible to allow a fair comparison, see Figure 8.

Figure 8. Three-dimensional models of the four buildings

Main modelling considerations included:

- Masonry compressive strength in the range of 2–3 MPa
- Elastic–plastic behaviour with distinct cracking and ultimate points
- Vertical and horizontal loads applied following EC1
- Flexible or semi-rigid diaphragm action depending on the floor system
- Lateral load patterns applied in both principal directions

- Capacity curves extended until global failure mechanisms developed

This approach helped highlight how each building transitions from elastic response to nonlinear cracking and eventual collapse.

4.2 General Behaviour from Capacity Curves

The capacity curves for all four dwellings show the same overall shape. Initially, the structures behave fairly stiffly due to the presence of continuous masonry walls. However, once diagonal cracking initiates, the stiffness drops rapidly, and the structures lose much of their load-carrying ability. Figure 9 depict the normalised capacity curves for all buildings

Figure 9. Normalised capacity curves for all buildings

Some common characteristics observed include:

- Base shear capacities that are generally low relative to building weight
- Premature shear failure in several critical piers
- Limited deformation capacity, with ductility values typically between 2 and 3
- Early strength degradation once the cracking threshold is reached
- Clear dominance of the transverse (Y) direction as the weakest axis

This indicates that none of the buildings can sustain large lateral displacements under strong shaking.

4.3 Performance Levels According to Eurocode 8

Performance evaluation was conducted by comparing the displacement capacities obtained from the capacity curves with the demand spectra defined by Eurocode 8. Two seismic hazard levels were considered:

- 95-year return period → Damage Limitation (DL)

- 475-year return period → Significant Damage (SD) and Near Collapse (NC)

Across all four buildings, the performance levels point to the same conclusion:

- DL is not satisfied.

The displacement demand for moderate earthquakes already exceeds the allowable limit for the onset of significant cracking.

- SD is exceeded.

For the design earthquake, the required displacement is far beyond the structures' capacity in both directions.

- NC is reached or surpassed.

In several cases, especially in the Y-direction, the buildings reach the Near Collapse point at relatively low drift levels. These results align with the observed field damage and confirm that the structures would be highly unsafe in future earthquakes without intervention.

Figure 10. Comparison of capacity vs spectra for the buildings

4.4 Comparison Between Directions

While both directions show weaknesses, the Y-direction stands out as the critical one for all case studies. This is mainly due to the lower density of transverse walls, more slender wall geometries, and the absence of effective confinement.

X-direction behaviour:

- Moderate initial stiffness
- Slightly higher shear capacity
- Still inadequate for EC8 requirements
- Ductility limited by brittle mechanisms

Y-direction behaviour:

- Lowest base shear resistance
- Early shear cracking
- Very limited post-cracking capacity

- Governs the overall seismic vulnerability

4.5 Summary of Analytical Deficiencies

The pushover analysis highlights several key deficiencies shared by all four URM dwellings:

- Insufficient shear strength
- Brittle and abrupt loss of stiffness after cracking
- Lack of effective diaphragm action
- Poor wall-to-wall and wall-to-slab connections
- Very low displacement capacity
- Inability to satisfy EC8 performance criteria even for moderate intensities

These analytical findings reinforce the damage patterns described earlier and justify the need for a comprehensive strengthening approach.

5. Strengthening Strategy

The damage patterns and analytical results discussed earlier make it clear that all four URM dwellings share the same structural weaknesses. Even though the buildings differ in size and layout, the underlying problems such as low shear resistance, poor connectivity between walls and slabs, and lack of confinement are common across the group. For this reason, a single strengthening concept was developed and then adapted slightly to each case. The goal of the retrofit strategy is to improve the overall seismic behavior of these houses while keeping the interventions practical and compatible with their original construction. The following subsections describe the main components of the strengthening approach.

5.1 General Objectives of the Retrofit

The retrofit solution was designed with several key objectives in mind, based on the requirements of Eurocode 8-3 and the specific behavior of URM structures in seismic regions:

- Increase the in-plane capacity of the main shear walls
- Improve wall–diaphragm interaction so the building can behave as a single box
- Reduce the likelihood of out-of-plane collapses
- Provide a more reliable load path for seismic forces
- Limit damage during moderate earthquakes and prevent collapse during stronger events
- Enhance global stiffness and improve the displacement capacity

These objectives reflect both the analytical findings and the typical failure mechanisms identified in the field.

5.2 Addition of Perimeter Reinforced-Concrete Columns

The most important intervention for all four buildings is the introduction of new reinforced-concrete (RC) perimeter columns, see Figure 11. These columns are placed at strategic wall edges, usually at corners or near long unbraced wall segments. They serve several purposes at once: they confine the masonry, improve vertical continuity, and significantly increase the building's ability to resist lateral loads.

Once connected properly to the foundation and the upgraded diaphragms, these columns become part of a new lateral-force-resisting system that works together with the remaining masonry.

Figure 11. Reinforced plan (a) and column details (b) for building A retrofit

5.3 Local Strengthening of Masonry Walls

In walls where the material was particularly weak or where damage had progressed too far, additional strengthening was included. This typically consisted of thin RC jacketing layers (around 8–10 cm thick) or, in smaller areas, local rebuilding of severely damaged masonry, see Figure 12.

The intention of these measures is to:

- increase the shear strength of the wall
- improve its ductility
- prevent the reappearance of sliding cracks
- provide additional out-of-plane stability

RC jacketing is connected to the existing wall using steel anchors to ensure that both materials act together.

Figure 12. Reinforced wall details for building B retrofit

5.4 Diaphragm Reinforcement and Box-Action Restoration

One of the main issues observed in all four dwellings was the lack of effective diaphragm action, see Figure 13. To address this, the retrofit includes:

- construction of new reinforced-concrete slabs where old or damaged diaphragms existed
- installation of steel beams or stiffening ribs where RC slabs cannot be added
- creation of continuous ring beams around the perimeter to tie the floors together

These measures help the building behave as a unified box rather than a collection of loosely connected walls. Improved diaphragm stiffness also reduces torsional movements and makes the load distribution more predictable.

Figure 13. Reinforcing perimeter RC ring beams for building C retrofit

5.5 Strengthening of Wall–Slab Connections

To prevent the wall–slab separation that was repeatedly observed in the damage surveys, steel anchors or dowels are placed at regular intervals along the junctions between floors and walls. These connectors transfer lateral forces more effectively and keep the masonry engaged with the diaphragm during seismic motion.

This intervention plays a crucial role in avoiding out-of-plane failures, which tend to occur suddenly and without much warning.

5.6 Foundation Improvements

Although the existing foundations generally remained intact, they were often too shallow or lacked sufficient reinforcement to support the newly introduced RC elements, see Figure 14. For this reason, the retrofit includes:

- local widening and strengthening of existing footings
- addition of tie-beams to link isolated foundation segments
- creation of a more continuous foundation system that can support the perimeter columns

These improvements enhance overall stiffness and help distribute forces more evenly to the ground.

Figure 14. Reinforced foundation details for building D retrofit

5.7 Expected Impact of the Strengthening Measures

When combined, the interventions described above are expected to bring clear and consistent improvements in seismic performance across all four case study buildings. In particular, the retrofit should:

- significantly increase base shear capacity in both directions
- delay the onset of shear cracking
- avoid out-of-plane wall failures

- improve the ductility and energy-dissipation capacity
- eliminate corner separation
- reduce torsional effects due to diaphragm stiffening
- satisfy the performance objectives for both the 95-year and 475-year return-period earthquakes

These expected improvements are confirmed by the capacity curve comparisons presented in the next section.

6. Capacity Improvement after Strengthening

The strengthening measures applied to the four URM dwellings resulted in clear and consistent improvements in their seismic performance. By comparing the original and retrofitted capacity curves, it becomes apparent how each intervention contributed to increasing strength, stiffness, and overall deformation capacity. Although the exact numerical results vary slightly from one house to another, the general trends are similar enough that the group can be evaluated as a whole. The following sections summarize the main improvements observed after retrofitting.

6.1 General Observations from Before–After Comparison

Across all case studies, the strengthened buildings show a much more stable response under lateral loading. The most noticeable changes include:

- A considerable increase in the maximum base shear
- A slower drop in stiffness after cracking
- A larger displacement capacity before reaching critical performance levels
- A more favourable distribution of damage due to improved wall interaction
- The elimination of several brittle failure mechanisms that dominated the pre-retrofit response

The Y-direction, which was consistently the weakest across all buildings, shows the strongest improvement after strengthening.

6.2 Behaviour in the X Direction

In the longitudinal direction, the retrofitted buildings exhibit:

- A higher initial stiffness due to the addition of RC columns
- A larger base shear capacity and a noticeably higher yield point
- A more gradual transition into the nonlinear range
- Improved post-yield behaviour, largely due to enhanced confinement and better floor-wall connectivity

Figure 15 depict the capacity comparison for all building pre- and post-retrofit X-direction

Figure 15. Capacity comparison for all building pre- and post-retrofit X-direction

While the X direction was not as critical before strengthening, the retrofit still produces significant gains that help stabilize the overall response.

6.3 Behaviour in the Y Direction

The most striking improvements appear in the transverse direction. Before strengthening, the Y-direction curves showed early shear cracking and limited ductility. After retrofit:

- Base shear capacity often doubles
- Stiffness increases due to the creation of new vertical RC elements
- The ultimate drift capacity becomes significantly larger
- The performance point shifts from the Near Collapse range to the SD or DL range
- Failure mechanisms transition from brittle to more ductile behaviour

This demonstrates that the strengthening strategy directly addresses the main weaknesses identified in the assessment, see Figure 16.

Figure 16. Capacity comparison for all building pre- and post-retrofit Y-direction

6.4 Normalised Parameters and Performance Levels

When expressed in terms of dimensionless performance indicators (such as V/W ratio and ductility, see Table 1), the improvements become even clearer:

- V/W ratio: typically increases from ~0.08–0.12 to ~0.2–0.28
- Ductility μ : increases from roughly 1.2–1.8 to around 2–3.5
- Initial stiffness: shows a gain of about 60–80%
- Ultimate drift: noticeably improved in both directions

In terms of Eurocode 8 performance levels:

- DL (95-year) is satisfied after strengthening
- SD (475-year) is also satisfied without the building reaching NC
- The retrofitted structures show a safer and more predictable response

Table 1. Capacity parameters of original vs reinforced building models

Parameter	Before Retrofit	After Retrofit	Improvement
V/W ratio (X)	0.12–0.18	0.24–0.28	↑ 80–100%
V/W ratio (Y)	0.08–0.12	0.2–0.24	↑ 100–150%
Ductility μ	1.2–1.8	2.0–3.5	↑ 60–100%
Stiffness (kN/m)	Low	Medium–High	↑ 60–80%

6.5 Overall Interpretation

Taken together, the results show that the recommended strengthening measures not only improve individual components but also significantly enhance the global seismic performance of the structures. The buildings behave more uniformly, exhibit increased resistance and ductility, and avoid the collapse-prone mechanisms seen in the original configuration.

Based on it, the improvements follow the same pattern across all four houses, the study confirms that a typology-based retrofit strategy is practical and effective for URM dwellings of this category, especially in regions with similar construction practices to Kruja.

7. Conclusions

The four URM dwellings analysed in this study represent a very typical segment of the residential building stock found in Kruja and many other parts of Albania. Although each house was built separately and presents small differences in layout and detailing, their overall behaviour during the 2019 earthquake was remarkably similar. All of them suffered heavy structural damage, which can be traced back to the same underlying problems: weak masonry materials, poor wall connections, insufficient diaphragm action, and the complete absence of confinement elements.

The onsite inspections revealed a consistent pattern of failures, which included diagonal shear cracking and corner separation and out-of-plane displacement of façade walls. The nonlinear static analyses proved the observations because they demonstrated that the tested materials had low shear strength and showed limited ductility and failed to meet Eurocode 8 standards for displacement capacity. The building structure showed weaknesses in both longitudinal and transverse directions, but the transverse direction proved to be the most critical for all four buildings.

The proposed unified strengthening strategy serves as a solution for the existing problems. The entire group found the retrofit approach, which involved adding perimeter reinforced-concrete columns and improving floor diaphragms and upgrading connections between walls and slabs and locally strengthening deteriorated masonry, to be suitable for their needs. The capacity curves show that the retrofit delivers substantial improvements to stiffness and strength and deformation capacity. The strengthened configurations both meet performance requirements for 95-year and 475-year seismic events while preventing the collapse-prone behavior that the original structures exhibited.

This research work demonstrates that URM houses of this typology can benefit from a consistent and repeatable retrofit solution. By treating these dwellings as part of the same construction family, engineers and local authorities can adopt a more systematic approach to strengthening similar buildings in the region. This is particularly valuable for areas like Kruja, where many older masonry homes share the same vulnerabilities and require targeted measures to ensure an acceptable level of seismic safety.

Conflict of Interests

The authors would like to confirm that there is no conflict of interests associated with this publication and there is no financial fund for this work that can affect the research outcomes.

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